

Transforming the Management of Secondary Education in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State Through Artificial Intelligence and Digital Connectivity

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ABSTRACT: *The study examined transforming the management of secondary education in public secondary schools in Rivers State through artificial intelligence and digital connectivity. Two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study which adopted descriptive survey design. The entire population of the study consisted of 8,260 teachers in the 276 public secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 826 (366 male and 460 female) teachers representing 10% of the population was drawn from all the 23 local government areas in Rivers State through stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire entitled, "Transforming the Management of Secondary Education Through Artificial Intelligence and Digital Connectivity Questionnaire (TMSETAI &DCQ)" developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument which had 14 items was property validated and a reliability index of 0.82 was obtained through Cronbach Alpha approach. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while, z-test at 0.05 level of confidence was used to test the hypotheses. The results of the study showed that ways artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State include: automating administrative tasks; analysing large quantity of data for effective decision-making and promoting effective teachers/students interactions. The study equally revealed that, artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning in public secondary schools in Rivers State through: artificial intelligence driven adaptive learning systems, virtual teaching assistants and interactive simulations; assessing each students strengths/weaknesses through individualized learning systems; and providing tailored guidance, support and feedback on individual learning patterns/knowledge level. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn and the following recommendations among others were made: government should provide training on artificial intelligence and digital connectivity and their integration into the management of schools and school programmes for public secondary school administrators in Rivers State.*

KEYWORDS: *Artificial Intelligence, Digital Connectivity, Secondary Education, Transformation and Management.*

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INTRODUCTION

Background to Study

Secondary education is the middle level of education all over the world. It is the level of education after basic education and before tertiary education. The broad goals of secondary education according to Federal Republic of Nigeria in the National Policy on Education (2014:11) are to [1]: prepare the students for useful living within the society; and to also prepare them for higher education. Secondary education is a very important level of education because of the significant role it plays in the life of its recipients. Specifically, the objectives of secondary education according to FRN (2014:11) include to [1]:

- a. Provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a higher level irrespective of sex, social status, religious or ethnic backgrounds,
- b. Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles;
- c. Provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades.
- d. Develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world's cultural heritage.
- e. Inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence.
- f. Foster national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity.
- g. Raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals and live as good citizens; and
- h. Provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development.

These well spelt out objectives have not been adequately achieved in Nigeria. Management of secondary education in Nigeria is experiencing a lot of setbacks due to many challenges. These numerous challenges have limited the strength of secondary education from actualising its purpose and realising its objectives. These challenges include but are not limited to underfunding; inadequate infrastructure; poor staff motivation; insecurity, poor learning environment, high dropout rates, outdated curriculum; inadequate teacher training; inadequate supply of teachers; poor integration of modern technology and disparities in educational standards. These factors require urgent attention. They should be addressed in order to improve the quality of secondary education in Nigeria. According to [2] with the adoption of analysis of reports and articles on secondary education in Nigeria, there is no doubt that it is in dire need of transformation, if it would continue to maintain its relevance in both the educational and national development of the country.

Transforming secondary education demands for the introduction of relevant and sustainable changes in secondary education system in Nigeria. It will require altering the existing processes or methods to bring in new ideas or approaches [3]. Embarking on transforming secondary education is aimed at improving quality and accessibility; ensuring that curriculum aligns with contemporary needs of society, improving teachers' professional development, enhancing funding and efficient utilization of resources, as well as ensuring an inclusive and equitable education system. [4] averred that transforming education at this level can be approached from any of the following contexts: organizational, personnel, educational and technological transformations, in a strategic, sustainable and comprehensive manner.

The whole world is going digital, where digital technologies and artificial intelligence (AI) are integrated in the management of businesses and education. The management of secondary education can be transformed through artificial intelligence and digital connectivity. This implies leveraging modern technologies to create more personalized, efficient and engaging learning experiences in secondary schools. The management of secondary education in Rivers State is at a critical juncture, where it is necessary to adopt modern technologies to enhance the quality and accessibility of secondary education.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has tremendous capacity of transforming teaching, learning and administrative processes. It has the potential of enhancing teacher effectiveness, student engagement, student academic

performance, promotion of inclusivity, and streamlining of administrative tasks. The integration of AI and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education in Rivers State will help to address the numerous issues affecting the effectiveness of secondary education in the state. This research work will therefore investigate the potentials of AI and digital connectivity in transforming the management of secondary education in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The management of secondary education in Rivers State is facing a lot of challenges. These problems significantly impact negatively on effective service and quality education delivery in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Several efforts have been made through the formulation and implementation of different reforms aimed at improving quality education and educational outcomes at secondary level. [5] assert that numerous factors such as poor administration, infrastructural deficits, inadequate teaching staff, limited access to quality and modern educational resources, paucity of funds and so on persist. Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) and digital connectivity has the potential of promoting efficient and effective administration of secondary education. It also has the capacity of reducing the negative impacts of the various challenges currently facing secondary education in Rivers State. The problem of this study, therefore, is to examine how we can transform the management of secondary education in Rivers State through artificial intelligence (AI) and digital connectivity.

Aim and Objectives of Study

The aim of this study is to investigate how the management of secondary education in public secondary schools in Rivers State can be transformed through the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Identify how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Determine how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. How can the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education transform administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. How can the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female teachers on how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female teachers on how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformation is seen as a significant change in the form, method, nature or function of something. It involves altering existing processes, structures or systems to break barriers and achieve something new [6]. Transformation involves a sustained and comprehensive commitment to finding solutions to problems

and creating lasting changes. The evolution of modern technologies and best practices have constantly changed the story of organizations all over the world. The emergence of artificial intelligence in education has provided a breakthrough from traditional education models geared to the average student to more specific paths of progress in learning [7]. The integration of artificial intelligence in educational management has transformed education from primitive programmed teaching to sophisticated machine learning algorithms that can flexibly respond to learning needs.

Artificial intelligence according to [8] is broadly defined as the activity dedicated to making machines intelligent, with intelligence being the quality that enables an entity to function appropriately in its environment with foresight. AI involves the creation of systems and machines that simulate human behaviours like learning, reasoning, and problem solving. The fundamental purpose of AI according to [9] is to enable machines to exhibit traits traditionally associated with human intelligence.

Digital connectivity has tremendously promoted digital learning in Nigeria. According to [4] digital learning is emerging as a transformative force in Nigerian education, it is fundamentally reshaping how learners acquire knowledge and skills. While the country is battling with numerous challenges such as limited access to quality educational resources, crowded classrooms, and traditional teaching methods, digital connectivity has enhanced online learning platforms, thus bridged gaps and providing unprecedented opportunities for learners across the country. The combination of AI and digital connectivity has the potential of revolutionising education in Nigeria. The integration of AI and digital connectivity are very relevant in the administration of examinations and management of examination malpractice. According to [10]; [11] AI proctoring software can be used to control examination malpractice. It can aid effective conduct of examinations in schools [12]. It is seen as an innovative way of fixing some of our educational challenges. Digital connectivity involves the use of electronic gadgets such as computers, smartphones and tablets to improve the learning experiences, and make management of education efficient and effective. The integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can improve personalized learning, promote effective teaching and learning, enhance administrative efficiency, and improve access and quality education.

In a study on the impact of artificial intelligence on students' academic development by [13], it was revealed that artificial intelligence offers significant benefits, including personalized learning, improved academic outcomes, and enhanced student engagement. Artificial intelligence according to [14] plays a significant role in influencing students' academic development through enhancing personalized learning experiences, to intelligent tutoring systems that provide tailored guidance, support, and feedback based on individual learning patterns and knowledge levels. Artificial intelligence has the potential of transforming education and meeting the diverse needs of students [15]. Artificial intelligence according to [19] assesses each student's strengths and weaknesses through individualized learning systems, then tailors' information to close learning gaps.

Artificial intelligence is changing the way people learn and teach. AI tutors offer round-the-clock academic support to students; it increases educational accessibility for students. [14] assert that Artificial intelligence frees up teachers' time to enable them concentrate more on developing students in other areas like critical thinking, creativity, social and emotional intelligence.

The integration of AI and digital connectivity in secondary education would enhance administrative efficiency and effectiveness by automating. Administrative tasks such as grading, enrolling of students, collection of fees, communication, scheduling, and analysing vast quantity of data for effective decision making [16]. According to [17] the integration of AI and digital connectivity in the management of secondary schools has the potential to streamline administrative tasks and optimize budget allocations leading to more efficient utilization of financial resources. Artificial intelligence can assist in financial forecasting, enhance transparency and accuracy in financial reporting [18]. Artificial intelligence technology and digital connectivity allows school administrators to focus more on strategic planning and improving educational outcomes rather than being bothered by manual financial processes.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised 8,260 teachers in the 276 public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. A sample of 826 (366 male and 460 female) teachers representing 10% of the population was drawn from the 23 Local Government Areas in Rivers State, through the stratified random sampling technique. An instrument titled, "Transforming the Management of Secondary Education through Artificial Intelligence and Digital Connectivity Questionnaire (TMSETAI& DCQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire, which has 14 items was well validated by three senior colleagues (2 from Department of Educational Management and 1 from Tests and Measurement Department) at Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the Cronbach Alpha method which gave a reliability index of 0.82.

The items in the questionnaire were designed using the 4-point likert rating scale of strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). A criterion mean of 2.50 was determined as basis for accepting or rejecting an item. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while z-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: How can the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State?

TABLE 1. Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Teachers on how the Integration of AI and Digital Connectivity in the Management of Secondary Education Can Transform Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	How AI and digital connectivity can transform administration of secondary schools	Male teachers N = 360		Female teachers N = 440		Mean set	Remarks
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
1	Automating administrative tasks such as: grading, fees collection, enrolling, communication etc.	3.52	0.64	3.45	0.67	3.49	Agree
2	Analysing vast quantity of data, for effective decision-making	3.60	0.61	3.58	0.63	3.59	Agree
3	Enhancing financial forecasting, transparency/accuracy in financial reporting	3.48	0.66	3.54	0.64	3.51	Agree
4	Promoting effective administration of examinations.	3.56	0.62	3.50	0.66	3.53	Agree
5	Promotion of effective teacher-student interactions.	3.50	0.65	3.40	0.69	3.45	Agree
6	Monitoring regularity/punctuality of teachers to school.	3.46	0.67	3.42	0.71	3.44	Agree
7	Monitoring regularity/punctuality of students to school.	3.44	0.69	3.42	0.71	3.43	Agree
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	3.51	0.65	3.47	0.67		

Table 1 shows high mean scores ranging from 3.40-3.60 indicating that majority of the respondents accepted all the items as ways artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State. The aggregate mean of 3.51 and 3.47 for male and female teachers respectively, which are very high and close, indicate that the respondents unanimously agreed on the items as ways. Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Therefore, artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform administration of secondary schools through: automating administrative tasks such as grading, fees collection, enrolling, communication etc;

analysing vast quantity of data for effective decision-making; promoting financial forecasting, transparency/accuracy in financial reporting; promoting effective administration of examinations; promotion of effective teacher-student interactions; and monitoring regularity/punctuality of teachers and students.

Research Question Two: How can the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

TABLE 2. Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Teachers on how the Integration of AI and Digital Connectivity Can Transform Teaching and Learning Outcomes in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	How AI and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning outcomes in secondary schools	Male teachers N = 360		Female teachers N = 440		Mean set	Remarks
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
1	Artificial intelligence driven tools and digital platforms can transform teaching and learning through AI-driven adaptive learning systems virtual teaching assistants and interactive simulations.	3.54	0.66	3.52	0.68	3.53	Agree
2	Artificial intelligence and digital platforms frees up teachers time to enable them pay more attention to developing students' critical thinking, creativity, emotional intelligence etc.	3.50	0.68	3.44	0.71	3.47	Agree
3	Artificial intelligence tools provide tailored guidance, support and feedback on individual learning patterns/knowledge levels.	3.52	0.67	3.48	0.69	3.50	Agree
4	Artificial intelligence assesses each students strength/weaknesses through individualized learning systems and tailors information to close learning gaps	3.48	0.70	3.42	0.73	3.45	Agree
5	Digital connectivity enhances online learning platforms thus providing unlimited access to educational opportunities for learners.	3.42	0.73	3.40	0.74	3.41	Agree
6	Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity provide round-the-clock academic support for teachers' professional development.	3.46	0.71	3.52	0.68	3.49	Agree
7	Artificial intelligence and digital platforms are everywhere in public secondary schools in Rivers State but they have not enhanced school teaching and learning.	2.38	0.75	2.36	0.76	2.37	Disagree
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	3.33	0.70	3.31	0.71		

Data in table 2 show that items 1 to 6 have high mean scores ranging from 3.40 to 3.54 indicating that the respondents accepted items 1 to 6 as ways Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Item 7 was rejected by the respondents. The aggregate mean of 3.33 and 3.31 for male and female respondents respectively which are very close reveal that the respondents shared a common opinion on how the integration of Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Therefore artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning through: artificial intelligence driven adaptive learning systems, virtual teaching assistants, and interactive simulations; artificial intelligence and digital platforms frees up teachers' time to enable them pay more attention to other things; artificial intelligence tools provide tailored guidance, support and feedback on individual learning patterns/knowledge levels: artificial intelligence assesses each student's strength/weaknesses through individual learning systems; digital connectivity enhances online learning platforms; artificial intelligence and digital connectivity provide round-the-clock academic support for teachers' professional development.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female teachers on how the integration of Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

TABLE 3. Z-Test of Difference in the Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Teachers on How the Incorporation of AI and Digital Connectivity in the Management of Secondary Education Can Transform the Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-critical	Level of sign.	Decision
Male teachers	360	3.51	0.65	798	0.854	±1.960	0.05	Ho ₁ not significant
Female teachers	440	3.47	0.67					

Table 3 shows the z-test analysis of difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on how the adoption of Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State. The result indicated that z-calculated value of 0.854 is by far less than the z-critical value of ±1.960 at 798 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained. This implies that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform the administration of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

TABLE 4: Z-Test of Difference in the Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Teachers on how the Integration of AI and Digital Connectivity in the Management of Secondary Education Can Transform the Teaching and Learning Outcomes in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-critical	Level of sign.	Decision
Male teachers	360	3.33	0.70	798	0.399	±1.960	0.05	Ho ₂ not significant
Female teachers	440	3.31	0.71					

Table 4 shows the z-test analysis of difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on how the incorporation of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The result reveals that the z-calculated value of 0.399 is by far less than the z-critical value of ±1.960 at 798 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Based on this, the null hypothesis was retained. The searcher therefore, upholds that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on how the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education can transform teaching and learning outcomes in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that, artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform administration of secondary schools through: automating administrative tasks such as grading, fees collection, enrolling, communication etc, analysing vast quantity of data for effective decision-making; promoting financial forecasting, transparency and accuracy in financial reporting; promoting effective administration of examination; promotion of effective teacher-student interactions; and monitoring of regularity/punctuality of teachers and students. Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity have the potentials of transforming the administration of public secondary schools because most administrative tasks can be carried out by artificial intelligence automated tools with high degree of efficiency and effectiveness. These findings are supported by [16]; [17] and [18].

A lot of tasks carried out by human beings are now effectively carried out by artificial intelligence. Things like grading of students, enrolling of students, collection of school fees, communication to parents, financial forecasting, accountability/accuracy in financial reporting etc can be effectively executed by artificial intelligence and digital tools. Artificial intelligence and digital platforms can enhance effective administration of examinations, thus serving as an effective means of controlling examination malpractice in internal and external examinations in secondary schools. They are equally effective in managing teachers and students attendance to school. Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity promotes access to quality education and they provide solutions to some of the challenges facing secondary education in Rivers State.

The study equally revealed that artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning through: artificial intelligence driven adaptive learning systems, virtual teaching assistants, and interactive simulations; artificial intelligence and digital platforms frees up teachers' time to enable them pay more attention to other things like development of critical thinking, creativity, social and emotional intelligence skills in students; artificial intelligence tools provide tailored guidance, support and feedback on individual learning patterns/knowledge levels; artificial intelligence assess each student's strengths/weaknesses through individual learning systems; digital connectivity enhances online learning platforms, artificial intelligence and digital connectivity provide round-the-clock academic support for teachers' professional development. Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can transform teaching and learning by providing an inclusive method of teaching and learning that meets the learning needs and knowledge level of every student.

The potentials of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity to transform teaching and learning are supported by [14]; [15]. Artificial intelligence promotes personalized learning and interactive simulations which provide more engaging and effective learning experience. Artificial intelligence powered counselling system can provide personalized guidance to students, identify students who are at risk of poor academic performance and provide timely intervention. Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity has expanded access to quality teaching and learning; quality educational resources and unlimited educational opportunities. Thus bridging geographical and socio-economic divides.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study has revealed the potentials of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity to transform the management of secondary education in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Artificial intelligence and digital connectivity can provide solutions to a lot of challenges affecting the effectiveness of secondary school administration, and quality of education in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Currently, the level of integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of secondary education in Rivers State is very low. This implies that these schools are yet to adequately leverage on artificial intelligence and digital connectivity potential benefits to improve and transform their administrative, teaching and learning procedures. There is therefore, an urgent need for Rivers State government to strategically invest massively on artificial intelligence technology and digital connectivity to enhance the integration of artificial intelligence and digital connectivity in the management of public secondary schools in the state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Rivers State government should invest massively on artificial intelligence technology and digital connective in public secondary schools in the state.
2. The state government should provide training on artificial intelligence and digital connectivity and their integration into the management of schools and school programmes for school administrators.
3. Government should organize artificial intelligence training programme for secondary school teachers in the state to equip them with relevant skills on the utilization of artificial intelligence technology and digital connectivity in teaching and learning.

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